

THE IMPORTANCE OF GAME TECHNOLOGIES IN FORMING PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE MUSIC TEACHERS

Annakulova Dildora

Syrdarya region pedagogues to new methods
teacher of music science at the national training center
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Abstract: This article discusses the importance of using game technologies in shaping the professional competence of future music teachers.

Key words: Educational system, music culture, technology, pedagogue, professional competence.

In the conditions of the market economy, being able to withstand the fierce competition that takes priority in the labor market requires professional competency from every specialist and requires continuous improvement. So, what is comprehensibility? What are the qualities of professional competence? What qualities of competence should the editor be able to highlight in himself? What is the importance of game technologies in the development of the professional competency of future music teachers in higher educational institutions of editing? We aim to talk about these and similar thoughts in this place.

In the dictionary of foreign words, the concept of "competence" is defined as a set of powers and rights of a person or institution, or a set of tasks and questions related to a certain person.

The French word "somretent" means "competent, competent".

The Latin word "comretencia" means "one who knows well", "having experience".

The suffix "nost" in Russian "komretentlik" means the degree of possession of any quality, therefore the term "komretentlik" is used to describe the quality and its level of development.

The English term "somretense" literally means "ability". In terms of content, "the effective use of theoretical knowledge in the activity, high-level professional competence, skill and talent can be demonstrated.

Comprehension-oriented education was developed by the American linguist I. N. Chomsky (1965, University of Massachusetts). In the program of the Symposium of the Soviet Union held in Bern (1996), the word "competency" was included among concepts such as "education", "skill", "ability".

In the Joint Declaration of the European Ministers of Education convened in Bologna (1999), the concerted basis of educational reforms was defined as a co-retentive basis.

The concept of "comretency" entered the field of education as a result of the scientific research of psychologists. From a scientific-psychological point of view, competence is how a specialist behaves in unconventional situations, in unexpected situations, how to communicate, take a new path in relations with opponents, perform ambiguous tasks, use information full of contradictions and continuously develop. and movement occurs in complex processes.

Professional competence does not mean the acquisition of separate knowledge and skills by a specialist, but the mastering of integrative knowledge and actions in each independent direction. At the same time, comretention allows you to constantly enrich your professional knowledge, use new modern information, understand important social requirements, search for new information, process it and apply it in your work.

Professional competence is expressed in the following conditions:

- in complex processes;
- performing unclear tasks;
- using conflicting information;
- being able to have an action plan in an unexpected situation.

Types of comretentive models:

- Professional value;
- Professional skills and qualifications
- Professional understanding and excellent knowledge.

The professional competence of future music teachers is not formed by itself, but there are stages of its formation, and on the basis of these stages, educational personnel are educated and formed. They consist of the following steps:

Formative stages of the future music teacher's competence

- determination of editorial and musical ability;
- education and formation;
- drying (giving a small amount of crackling);
- believe.

The editorial personnel of higher education institutions use science, experience, self-expression based on abilities and professional skills plays an important role in effective audience management.

There are specific tasks of managing the process in the modern editor's office of higher education institutions, which are as follows:

- design;
- organization of processes;
- innovative management of activities;
- giving motivation;
- control;
- analysis.

Below, the essence of reflective qualities on the basis of professional competence will be briefly explained.

1. Social competence - the ability to show activity in social relations, the ability to communicate with subjects in professional activities.

2. Special competence - preparation for the organization of professional-edagogical activity, correct solution of professional-edagogical problems, realistic assessment of activity results, sequential development of knowledge, qualifications and skills, psychological, methodical on the basis of this competence , informative, creative, innovative and communicative competence is noticeable. They express the following content:

a) psychological competence - creating a healthy psychological environment in the educational process, organizing positive communication with students and other participants

of the educational process, being able to understand and eliminate various negative psychological disagreements at the right time;

b) methodical competence - methodically rational organization of the editorial process, correct determination of the forms of educational or educational activity, ability to choose tools and methods in accordance with the purpose, know how to effectively use methods;

d) information literacy - searching, collecting, sorting, processing and effectively using necessary, important, necessary, useful information in the information environment;

e) creative competence - a creative and critical approach to editorial activity, being able to demonstrate one's own creative skills;

f) innovative competence - putting forward new ideas on improving the editorial process, improving the quality of education, increasing the effectiveness of the educational process, and successfully implementing them into practice;

g) communicative competence - being able to have a sincere dialogue with all participants of the educational process, as well as students, listen to them and have a positive influence.

3. Personal competence - consistently achieving professional growth, increasing the level of qualifications, demonstrating one's business potential in professional activities.

4. Technological competence is the mastery of advanced technologies that enrich musical editorial skills, knowledge, and skills, effective use of modern tools, techniques, and technologies.

5. Extreme prudence - to make rational decisions in emergency situations (natural disasters, technological process failure), when editorial disputes arise, to follow the rules of correct movement.

It is important to work on oneself and develop one's self in order to gain professional and editorial competence for the future music teacher in higher education institutions. Self-development tasks are determined through self-analysis and self-evaluation.

One of the important tasks in giving a modern touch to the musical education process in the department of "Musical Education" of higher educational institutions is to equip future music teachers with professional-pedagogical knowledge, qualifications and skills, future musicians is to increase the quality of training of teachers, to form motivation for professional activity, to develop the professional training of future music teachers.

Modernization of higher educational institutions of pedagogy and the process of music education in them, improvement of the quality-monitoring of the system of training of pedagogical specialists, arming future teachers with modern professional qualifications, knowledge, and skills, acmeological in relation to professional activity in them formation of motivation is one of the important tasks in the process of formation of professional training of pedagogical specialists.

The experience of developed countries, in particular, Great Britain, Australia, Switzerland, Germany, Malaysia, and Canada, shows that the main task of professional education is to develop intelligence and logical thinking in students based on the specificity of the chosen specialty. consists of, and on the basis of the perfect performance of the given task, the professional training of the students is ensured. In this case, as the main criterion requirements of professional training, the practical readiness of music teachers for activities and the level of mastering of knowledge, skills and qualifications within the scope of specialization are aimed as adaptation to the requirements of professional activity.

Based on the analysis of the scientific ideas presented above, it can be said that the professional competence of the future music teacher in the higher educational institutions of pedagogy is formed and manifested in the process of practical activity. The professional competence of the teacher in the organization of the musical education process is reflected in his educational and methodological activities, in the effective use of innovative educational technologies, in the consistent use of game technologies, as well as in his ability to eliminate editorial conflicts.

Great attention is paid to game technologies in the practice of musical education. The theory of game technologies is inextricably linked with the theory of other educational technologies. R.Ya., famous thinkers of game technologies. Galrerins, L.S. Vygodsky, A.N. Theoretically based on the works of Leontev.

Game technologies, according to their nature, serve as the main practical means of forming the personal qualities of future teachers. Game technologies as a means of learning and teaching flourished in the 20s of the 20th century. Games imitating game technologies were recognized as a means of learning.

A.A. Verbisky looks at game technologies as sign-contextual forms of education. According to Verbisky, the activity of training in game technologies and future professional activity is a model or its prototype, as a means of some artificial and natural knowledge and teaching. Therefore, game technologies are defined as sign models of professional activity, and its content is given with the help of sign tools, that is, modeling, imitation and communication, including natural language.

A.A. The task of the Verbisky higher education institution in this kind of education, at the same time, the student is directed (mastered) the method, motive, purpose, means, methods and results of the activity from one type of activity (education) to another (professional) type.) is understood as providing transfer.

The basis of the use of game technologies is the activation and acceleration of students. According to the studies of scientists, the game is one of the main types of activity together with work and study. According to psychologists, the psychological mechanisms of playful activity rely on the fundamental needs of a person to express himself, stabilize his place in life, manage himself, and realize his potential.

The game is defined as a type of activity in situations aimed at mastering and re-creating social experiences, and it develops and improves a person's behavior control.

L.S. Vygodsky clearly describes the game as a child's working social world, a means of mastering abilities. D.N. According to Uznadze, play is a form of immanent psychological (spiritual) behavior characteristic of a person. L.S. Vygodsky describes the game as a means of mastering the social world of the child, social orders.

A.N. Leontev views the game as the freedom of a person to realize his unrealizable interests (interests) in his imagination.

Psychologists say that the ability to get into the game does not depend on a person's age, but the game is unique for each age person.

Although game technologies have different forms, according to their content, all of them are directed towards a single goal, that is, they deepen and expand the theoretical knowledge of students, and create the skills to use the acquired theoretical knowledge independently and effectively in practice. It fulfills the task of preparing them for coordination

of socio-economic relations, development of social activity, development of mature moral qualities, development of a perfect person with a deep and healthy mind and broad outlook.

Game activities are dedicated to performing certain functions. They are as follows:

- ❖ *realizing their potential*
- ❖ *communication (organizational)*
- ❖ *charm*
- ❖ *treatment*
- ❖ *diagnosis*
- ❖ *socialization*
- ❖ *international communication*

In the process of musical education, game technologies are used in the form of a didactic game lesson. In these lessons, the learning process of students is coordinated through game activities. For this reason, lessons in which musical learning activities of students are combined with game activities are called didactic game lessons.

Didactic games allow to repeat and change game methods without doubt, to introduce various innovations to it. As a result, it made it possible to achieve uniform and solid skills of the game, at the same time, to be able to listen to each of its rules and to achieve compliance with it. Types of didactic games serve the task of teaching music, increase enthusiasm, and are conducted in an understandable way for the participants. The future music teachers practice with all their heart in order to become the winner, they get used to doing every given task, as a result, their enthusiasm for doing didactic tasks increases. Types of didactic games are expressed in a better understanding of the purpose of music lessons and the tasks of each exercise.

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